

Political Economy of Pandemics

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Desire to make a huge profit could be one of the main reasons for the outbreaks of zoonotic diseases or zoonoses¹, as well as epidemics, as well as pandemics like COVID-19. The aim of this writing is not to do review what political economy studies on effects of pandemics on national economies or international economy, but, is to pay the particular attention to one of the root causes of Pandemics, namely, the question of genetic diversity and similarity in intensive livestock farming (hereafter ILF). While most of the academic research works pay attention to the economic aftermath of pandemics, this concise writing will try to bring the question in academic sphere from the perspective of political economy, which is comparatively a very less celebrated issue in academic writings.

A Political-Economic Background of Pandemics

As it is known that against the high-speed growth rate of the human

¹ Zoonotic disease or "a zoonosis is any disease or infection that is naturally transmissible from vertebrate animals to humans (WHO, 2020)."

population, the global economy grew geometrically in past few decades; therefore, in order to reply to the changing consumer behaviour, especially the increased demand of dairy and meat products has triggered the rapid development and expansion of ILF or factory farming (Sere et al., 1996; FAO, 2007; Vale, 2019; UNEP 2020). Due to the environment of intensive livestock farms (Stevenson, 2017), pathogens may use livestock as a bridge between wild animals and humans (Liverani, et al. 2013; UNEP, 2020), and this process particularly starts from informal markets (UNEP, 2020). Pathogens need to keep changing hosts in order to survive (Alberts, 2002; UNEP, 2020); but, a pathogen may face more resistance, and couldn't dominate in a diverse population (FAO, 2007; Liverani et al., 2013; IPES-Food, 2017; UNEP 2020).

Genetic Engineering in ILF and Pathogen

Intensive livestock farming or factory farming implements genetic manipulation or gene editing in order to produce more products with same production costs (FAO, 2007; Stevenson, 2017; IPES-Food, 2017), where animals are treated like machines (Stevenson, 2017), and it frequently utilises a narrow range of breeds (FAO, 2007; Stevenson, 2017; IPES-Food, 2017). Thus, mainly the rapid spread of intensive livestock production is the most significant threat to genetic diversity (Sere et al., 1996; FAO, 2007; Vale, 2019). It can generate genetic similarities (Liverani et al., 2013; Vale, 2019; UNEP, 2020), especially in herds and flocks (UNEP, 2020), and in consequence, it reduces resilience and makes them susceptible to pathogens (Liverani et al., 2013; UNEP, 2020); while genetic diversity increases, the disease resistance in animals increases and decreases the chances of outbreaks of zoonotic diseases (FAO, 2007; IPES-Food, 2017; UNEP, 2020).

Political Economy of Profit

When all these destructive consequences of factory farming are known; then our curious minds want to know, why all these are still continuing? The possible answer we may find, if we see the characteristics of profit through the eyes of Dunning (1860), as he states: "With adequate profit, capital is very bold. A certain ... 300 per cent., and there is not a crime at which it will scruple, nor a risk it will not run, even to the chance of its owner being hanged."

Postlude

Under all these circumstances, we can make a statement that human economic activities and uses of scientific knowledge in the farming must be justified by the epistemology of political economy, where its character will be defined or inspired by the question of the

emancipation from the reckless desire of capital accumulation. And, a further detailed political-economic study based on this ethics is crucially needed, as political economy itself is characterised by the true interdisciplinarity.

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